

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

A study to assess the knowledge regarding prevention of substance abuse among high school students in selected school in Mangalore

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Abstract

Substance use disorders in the united states recently reached epidemic proportions (Center for disease control and prevention) [2017]. Substance abuse in society an estimated 600 billion annually from loss of productivity, health care utilization costs, and criminal justice cost (National institute on drug abuse 2016) .It affects the individual from all walks of life regardless of race, gender, geographic location, or socio economic status.

Objectives of the study: To assess the level of knowledge among high school students regarding prevention of substance abuse. To find the association between knowledge score with selected demographic variables.

Method: A descriptive survey approach was considered suitable for this study the aim of the study was to evaluate the knowledge of high school students regarding prevention of substance abuse. Research approach tells the researchers from whom the data is to be collected, how to collect and how to analyse the data. It also suggests the possible conclusion and helps the researcher in answering specific research question in the most accurate and efficient way possible. Research design is the overall plan for obtaining answer to the question being studied and handling some of the difficulties encountered during the research process. To accomplish the objectives of the study a descriptive survey was used to assess the knowledge towards prevention of substance abuse among high school students. Setting is the physical location and condition in which data take place. The study is conducted in a selected school in Mangalore. The population is high school students of a selected school in Mangalore that have one or more characteristics in common that are of interest to the researcher. Sample is subset of population selected to participate in research study. The sample for the present study was 30 male and female students from a selected school of Mangalore.

Results: assessing the knowledge of high school regarding prevention of Substance abuse. The Discussion is described under the following heading. Description of demographic variable of high school students. Analysis of knowledge of high school students regarding prevention of substance abuse. SECTION 1: Description of demographic variable of high school students. 70% of students in the age group 14 years and 30% were in the age group of 15 years. 30% were Christians , 46.7% were Hindus and 23% were Muslims .23.3%of students parents are doing business , 76.7%were coolies, 6.7% are Professionals and 13.3% unemployed .70% of the Students get the knowledge regarding prevention of substance abuse from internet , 6.7%of them from newspaper 20%of students from teachers and only 3.3% get knowledge from other services. The results shows that the highest percentage (46.6%), of the sample had an good level of knowledge whose score ranged between 14-20 and 23.35 % of the sample had poor knowledge.

Keywords: Knowledge; Prevention; Substance abuse; High school student; Disorder

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1. Introduction

In the present study, ever use of substance as well as distributions among the high school students were comparable to the findings of the studies where we noted. A majority of the user reported trying to the end of the habit and most of the users expressed a desire to quit the habit. It reveals that all users didn't want to continue the habit and they held a positive attitude towards quitting therefore, motivation on the part of the family, friends, and close ones could help the users to come out from the habit. Easy availability of the substances especially the licit once, has been the most common reason for continuation followed by relief from stress and acceptability among students. [1] This shows that addicted peoples furnished high school students with ways to procure and continue using substance. Moreover as high school students are in a transitional phase confusion can some time make them susceptible to taking unfavorable habits. In contrast to this, factors leading to quitting substances use also exist in and around high school students can indirectly motivated the user to give up the habit. Knowledge regarding the harmful effects of substances use is, as the major reasons stated were moral sense and fear of health problems, which clearly suggest that attitude shaping by parents and knowledge of harmfulness of use considerably high among the users, particularly for licit ones such as tobacco, alcohol and cannabis. [2] Where the users are not deprived of the knowledge regarding consequences of consumption of substances. Particularly disturbing is the fact that they continue their use despite knowing the effects. This information has been provided through the medias, principally the television and hoarding. A small percentage also reported being taught about it in school and by family members. Therefore, media and close contacts are the primarily responsible for imparting knowledge, whether it be pro- or anti-substance abuse and these findings are common anywhere. [3] Users are Mainly responsible for influencing their peers and close contacts in to taking up the habits, as is seen in present study as well as in other studies. Influence of peers and close contacts who use substances are usually responsible for initiating their use in others and this is evident in the present study and related studies. Where users have been accountable for instigating the habit. [4]

2. Material and methods

2.1. Research approach

Research approach tells the researchers from whom the data is to be collected, how to collect and how to analyse the data. It also suggests the possible conclusion and helps the researcher in answering specific research question in the most accurate and efficient way possible. A descriptive survey approach was considered suitable for this study the aim of the study was to evaluate the knowledge of high school students regarding prevention of substance abuse.

2.1.1. Research design

Research design is the overall plan for obtaining answer to the question being studied and handling some of the difficulties encountered during the research process. To accomplish the objectives of the study a descriptive survey was used to assess the knowledge towards prevention of substance abuse among high school students.

2.1.2. Setting of the study

Setting is the physical location and condition in which data take place. The study is conducted in a selected school in Mangalore.

2.1.3. Population

The population is high school students of a selected school in Mangalore that have one or more characteristics in common that are of interest to the researcher.

2.1.4. Sample

Sample is subset of population selected to participate in research study.

2.1.5. Sampling technique

The sample for the present study was 30 male and female students from a selected school of Mangalore.

3. Results

3.1. Organization of findings

The data analyzed are presented under the following sections:

- Section-01: Description of demographic variables of high school students
- Section-02: Analysis the knowledge of high school students regarding the prevention of substance abuse

3.2. Section-01: Description of demographic variables of high school students

Table 1 Frequency and percentage distribution of the high school students according to demographic characteristics

SL.NO	Demographic values	Frequency	Percentage
1	Age of student		
	14years	21	70%
	15 years	9	30%
2	Religion		
	Christian	9	30%
	Hindu	14	40.7%
	Muslim	7	23.3%
3	Sources		
	Any other	1	33%
	Internet	21	70%
	Newspaper	2	6.7%
	Teacher	6	20%
4	Occupation of the parents		
	Business	7	23.3%
	Coolie	17	56.7%
	Professional	2	6.7%
	Unemployed	4	13.3%

The above table depicts the frequency and percentage distribution of high school children according to age of student, religion, sources and occupation of the parents.

3.3. Section-02: Analysis the knowledge of high school students regarding the prevention of substance abuse

Table 2 Determine the level of knowledge score of high school students regarding prevention of substance abuse

Knowledge level	Score	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Poor	0-6	7	23.33
Average	7-13	9	30
Good	14-20	14	46.67

The result shows the height percentage (46.67) of the sample had an average level of knowledge whose score ranged between 7-13 and 23.3% of the sample had poor knowledge.

4. Discussion

The study focused on as

Assessing the knowledge of high school regarding prevention of Substance abuse. The Discussion is described under the following heading.

- Description of demographic variable of high school students.
- Analysis of knowledge of high school students regarding prevention of substance abuse.

4.1. Section 1

- Description of demographic variable of high school students.
- 70% of students in the age group 14 years and 30% were in the age group of 15 years. 3) 30% were Christians 46.7% were Hindus and 23% were Muslims.
- 23.3%of students' parents are doing business, 76.7% were coolies, 6.7% are Professionals and 13.3% unemployed.
- 70% of the Students get the knowledge regarding prevention of substance abuse from internet, 6.7% of them from newspaper 20%of students from teachers and only 3.3% get knowledge from other services.

4.2. Section 2

Analysis of knowledge of high school students regarding prevention of substance abuse

Table 3 Percentage and grade of high school students regarding substance abuse

Percentage	Grade
28.33	Poor
30	Average
46.67	Good

5. Conclusion

The following conclusion are drawn based on the findings of the present study: Assessment of the level of knowledge of the high school student showed that the 30% of sample had average knowledge, 46.67% of the student had good knowledge and 23.33% of the student had poor knowledge. Association of knowledge of prevention of substance abuse and demographic variables indicates that there was no significant association between knowledge scores of high school students with demographic variables. Hence the study concluded that the students have adequate knowledge regarding prevention of substance abuse .There was necessity to give health education for students to improve their knowledge and attitude related to substance abuse.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

References

- [1] N. Mercy, R. Kyle, Medical surgical nursing, Jannetti Publication : 87
- [2] Jens Christober .skogen, experience and knowledge regarding illicit drug . use 2014 Kevin m Grus Child psychol . psychiatric jan 2018
- [3] Khan , Blance prevalence of alchol and depece on conditions in adrscene , 2013
- [4] Ahmed HG , hassans,M prevalence of substance abuse among adrescent , journal of addict Behav ,2013.